

Kinetics of Chemisorption of Hydrogen on Iron Powder—Application of Elovich Equation

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The kinetics of hydrogen chemisorption on iron powder has been investigated in the temperature range 56°–300° under conditions of constant pressure and constant volume. The data have been analysed through the Elovich equation and a model consisting of three different types of sites has been proposed. The results are consistent with this model.

THE evaluation of the heterogeneous nature of solid adsorbents has been the subject of numerous investigations, experimental as well as theoretical. Activity towards cumene cracking¹, sorption of ethylene², determination of the infrared spectrum of adsorbed molecules³ and temperature variation chemisorption of hydrogen⁴ are some of the important experimental methods employed for the elucidation of site distribution on solid surfaces. Quantum mechanical calculations⁵ have also been carried out to evaluate the energy distribution among sites. Analysis of chemisorption kinetic data through the Elovich equation⁶ has often yielded evidence for surface heterogeneity. In recent communications from this laboratory^{7,8}, examination of the first minute chemisorption (usually designated as fast chemisorption) data has indicated the participation of different sites on the surface in the chemisorption process. The present communication deals with the application of the Elovich equation to the chemisorption kinetic data of hydrogen on iron powder.

The adsorbent was obtained by reducing ferric oxide (Fe₂O₃) at 480° in a stream of pure dry hydrogen for 100 hrs. The ferric oxide itself was obtained by the decomposition of analar grade ferric nitrate. The adsorption measurements were carried out in a conventional volumetric apparatus.

The kinetic data were first obtained at a constant pressure of one atm. at different temperatures in the range 56°–300°. This was followed by a series of kinetic measurements under conditions of constant volume by varying the initial pressure of hydrogen, the temperature being maintained constant at 200°. The experimental data were analysed by applying the linear form of the Elovich⁶ equation :

$$q = \frac{1}{\alpha} \ln(t+t_0) - \frac{1}{\alpha} \ln t_0$$

where q is the amount adsorbed in ml NTP, t , the time, in minutes, α and t_0 are constants, t_0 being equal to $1/\alpha\alpha$, where a is another constant. A few

typical plots obtained under conditions of constant pressure are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Typical Elovich Plots for the kinetics of Chemisorption of Hydrogen on Iron Powder (pressure = 1 atm.).

Data at Constant Pressure :

Table I summarises the values of the Elovich constant α for each stage of the adsorption together

TABLE I—DATA AT CONSTANT PRESSURE					
Temperature °C	q_1 ml NTP	q_{120} ml NTP	α_1	α_2	t_b min
56	0.28	0.73	23.72	5.76	19.95
78	0.35	0.91	19.35	6.14	10.00
100	0.48	1.07	10.47	6.45	6.45
134	0.61	1.08	10.13	—	—
162	0.70	1.12	11.75	—	—
200	0.88	1.33	16.12	7.14	19.05
250	0.91	1.30	19.81	7.21	22.00
300	1.00	1.33	19.45	11.05	30.00

with the values of t_b (the time in minutes at which the break in the Elovich plot occurs). It is seen from the table that the value of t_b decreases from

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19.95 mins. at 56° to 6.45 mins. at 100°. No break is noticed in the Elovich plot for the experiments at 134° and 162°. An increase in t_b is observed from 19.05 mins. at 200° to 30.00 mins. at 300°. The decreasing as well as increasing trends in the values of t_b on either side of an intermediate temperature range suggest the participation of different types of sites for the chemisorption of hydrogen. This is further reflected in the variation of the constants α_1 and α_2 with temperature.

To explain the observed kinetic data, a simple qualitative mechanism has been proposed. It is assumed that the surface consists of three kinds of sites denoted as S_1 , S_2 and S_3 . At lower temperatures (56° and 78°), the activity of the sites varied as $S_1 > S_2 \gg S_3$. As the temperature is increased, the S_2 sites acquire sufficient energy to show increased activity. At any given temperature, a time is reached at which S_1 sites are completely covered, the adsorption occurring predominantly on S_2 . An increase in temperature favours an early participation of S_2 sites thereby decreasing the value of t_b . This means that the initial rate itself is increased which is shown by the decrease in the value of α_1 , which is inversely proportional to the ambient rate.

At 134° and 162°, S_2 sites are activated to such an extent that it is no longer possible to distinguish between S_1 and S_2 sites. As the adsorption occurs simultaneously on S_1 and S_2 sites, Elovich plots do not show any break. At still higher temperatures, (200° and above) the S_3 sites are also brought into operation. However, in view of the decrease in the total adsorption with increase in temperature, it can be expected that the time required for the saturation of S_1 and S_2 is also enhanced, resulting in an increase in the values of t_b . It is interesting to note that the values of the constant α_2 increase in the range 56° to 300° (except at 134° and 162°, where no break is observed) indicating a decrease in the ambient rate on the least active sites (S_2 and later S_3), as the temperature is increased.

Data at Constant Volume :

Table 2 contains the values of the calculated constants α_1 and α_2 and t_b obtained from the Elovich plots for the kinetic experiments at 200°. The qualitative mechanism suggested above may be extended to explain the trend of the values in Table 2. At 200° the chemisorption of hydrogen takes place

TABLE 2—DATA AT CONSTANT VOLUME

Initial pressure mm. Hg	q_1 m.t.n c.c. NTP	q_{50} m.t.n c.c. NTP	temperature 200°		
			α_1	α_2	t_b min
152	0.52	0.61	36.19	—	—
290	0.74	0.90	24.08	—	—
406	0.87	1.08	18.03	—	—
466	0.96	1.22	27.63	14.05	6.30
570	0.97	1.25	25.33	10.74	7.08
603	0.98	1.28	17.67	10.59	7.90
720	1.05	1.41	13.60	9.67	13.49

on the highly active S_1 and S_2 sites (taken together) followed by the less active S_3 sites. As the volume of hydrogen admitted is varied in these series of experiments, it can be visualized that the sites associated with high heat of adsorption will be covered first. At low initial pressures (upto 400 mm Hg) the limited availability of the adsorbate would restrict the adsorption only to S_1 and S_2 sites. At pressures higher than 400 mm, the amount of adsorbate admitted is sufficient to cover all the S_1 and S_2 sites followed by the S_3 sites, the number of the S_3 sites participating in adsorption increasing with increase in initial pressure. The participation of S_3 sites in adsorption is evidenced by the break in the Elovich plots.

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